

CHANGES IN THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM THAT OCCUR WITH THE COMBINED USE OF ANTIHYPERTENSION DRUGS

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Abstract: In this article, the analysis of literature data on the clinical efficacy and safety of antihypertensive drugs shows that there is a significant difference between original and generic drugs, both in therapeutic equivalence and in the frequency and severity of adverse reactions caused by them.

Key words: arterial hypertension, antihypertensive drugs, original drug, generic, therapeutic equivalence, side effects.

Arterial hypertension (AH) is a long-term increase in blood pressure (BP) above 140/90 mm Hg. Art. arterial hypertension (systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respectively) in people who do not receive adequate antihypertensive therapy.

Hypertension is one of the leading risk factors for the development of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, the main cause of high mortality and disability in all countries, and the most common heart disease. The prevalence of hypertension is high throughout the world, 20-30% of the adult population in developed countries suffer from it. [4,5]

In Uzbekistan, hypertension occurs in 30-40% of the elderly population, and in people over 60 years old - up to 60-70%. The main types of arterial hypertension are essential hypertension of unknown etiology, which accounts for 90-95% of patients with hypertension, or arterial hypertension, and secondary hypertension - symptomatic, the cause of which may be kidney pathology (kidney damage), renal parenchyma, adrenal glands. glands (pheomocytoma, hyperaldosteronism), large vessels (renal artery stenosis, coarctation of the aorta). Isolated systolic hypertension is also distinguished, in which systolic blood pressure exceeds 160, and diastolic blood pressure is less than 90 mm Hg. Art. This form of hypertension occurs mainly in the elderly and is caused by a decrease in vascular elasticity. Adequate treatment of arterial hypertension should lead to a decrease in pressure to target values (140/90 mm Hg, in diabetes mellitus and kidney pathology - 130/80). The prognosis of hypertension depends not only on blood pressure. Of great importance are: the presence of concomitant risk factors: age, family history of early cardiovascular diseases, smoking, high cholesterol and lipid spectrum disorder in the blood

plasma, physical inactivity; weight gain; abdominal obesity, diabetes mellitus (DM), high doses of alcohol; the degree of damage to target organs and the presence of concomitant clinical conditions [7].

The main goal of hypertension treatment is to reduce mortality from cardiovascular diseases. Antihypertensive therapy strategies are developed to prevent damage to target organs and death associated with hypertension. In patients with high blood pressure, the greatest risk of developing myocardial infarction or stroke occurs when antihypertensive therapy is discontinued (even temporarily). According to a meta-analysis of many clinical studies, a decrease in systolic blood pressure by 12–13% leads to a decrease in cardiovascular complications by 21–37%. Adequate, regular antihypertensive therapy reduces mortality in patients: from myocardial infarction - by 15–20%, from stroke - by 40–50%. This explains the need for timely and justified treatment [6,7].

According to leading world experts, treatment of arterial hypertension should be as early and intensive as possible. Therefore, effective treatment often requires a combination of two or more antihypertensive drugs even in the early stages of the disease. Combined low doses of drugs are used in therapy, which reduces the risk of side effects; Acts simultaneously on various mechanisms of arterial hypertension, which increases the effectiveness of treatment; In addition, a fixed combination of two or more drugs allows for combination therapy with one tablet, which is more convenient for the patient [2,6]. The main groups of drugs for the treatment of arterial hypertension: First-line drugs (main): angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors; beta-blockers (BB); calcium channel blockers (Ca²⁺ antagonists); diuretics; angiotensin receptor blockers;

Second-line drugs (alternative): alpha-blockers; A₂-adrenergic receptor agonists and imidazoline receptors (central neurotropic agents, central sympatholytics), direct renin inhibitors.

Features of the main groups of antihypertensive drugs AAF inhibitors: more effective in young people; improve quality of life; organoprotective action (cardio-, nephrovasoprotective); prevention of diabetic nephropathy; slowing down the development of addiction; positive metabolic effects: improved glucose metabolism, increased sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin, does not affect lipid metabolism, urea or creatinine levels; no withdrawal syndrome; But! May cause cough in 11.5% of cases - with captopril, in 24.7% of cases - with enalapril, as a result of irritation of the afferent fibers of the vagus nerve of the upper respiratory tract due to impaired bradykinin metabolism may increase. Potassium levels in the blood and pathways that cause renal failure [5,6]. Beta-

blockers (BB): their effectiveness is high, especially in young people; they reduce mortality from coronary heart disease in non-smokers; reduction in the incidence of coronary heart disease and its development; reduction in mortality from myocardial infarction; But! may reduce high-density lipoprotein levels; causes sexual dysfunction in men; may have a negative effect on cognitive functions (lipophilic beta-blockers); peripheral vasoconstriction, bronchospasm (non-selective beta-blockers); high doses - bradycardia and heart failure. They cause withdrawal syndrome. Inexpensive drugs are available (propranolol). Thiazide diuretics: currently, diuretics occupy one of the leading positions among modern drugs for the long-term treatment of arterial hypertension; more effective in elderly patients; reduce the risk of stroke in smokers and non-smokers; delay the release of calcium and prevent pathological fractures in osteoporosis; high doses (dichlorothiazide above 25 mg) can reduce the amount of potassium in the plasma, cause impotence, increase the level of total cholesterol and low-density lipoproteins, glucose and urea, therefore they are not indicated for patients with hypokalemia, diabetes mellitus, gout. ; Important: low doses of hydrochlorothiazide and thiazide-like diuretics used to treat arterial hypertension (hydrochlorothiazide 12.5-25 mg) have a satisfactory safety profile, do not have a clinically significant effect on carbohydrate, lipid, purine and electrolyte metabolism and are well tolerated. received. patients, which allows for long-term therapy. Indapamide, unlike other thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics, has a minimal effect on potassium and uric acid levels, has virtually no effect on plasma glucose concentrations, does not impair the sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin, and is therefore the safest drug for treating hypertension in patients with diabetes mellitus and has a mild diuretic effect. Calcium channel blockers: very effective in treating hypertension, especially in the elderly; effective in ischemic heart disease, but virtually useless in post-infarction atherosclerosis; their advantages include lowering systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure without causing orthostatic hypotension; metabolically neutral - does not affect the lipid profile, carbohydrates, purine metabolism, or electrolyte balance); has antiplatelet activity; has a cardioprotective effect (more pronounced in verapamil and diltiazem); possible side effects associated with vasodilation - headache, dizziness, fever hot flashes, palpitations, temporary hypotension, peripheral edema of the legs, ankles, elbows - more typical for short-acting nifedipine; bradycardia, rare cases of heart failure (verapamil).

When prescribing drugs, the following main factors should be taken into account: drug efficacy, impact on quality of life, metabolism, drug price and its pharmacoeconomic and quality indicators, due to which its origin is very large. It is important whether the drug is original or reproduced (generic).

Generic drug - a generic drug replaced by a patented analogue (original drug) and released on the market after the expiration of the patent, protection of the original copy. Specific features of generics: obtaining a copy of the original drug, since the patent holder provides incomplete information about the original; low quality, efficiency and safety indicators; entering the market after the expiration of the patent protection of the original drug; lack of preclinical and clinical studies; usually uninformed instructions; circulation is permitted on the basis of a reduced volume of registration data and bioequivalence assessment data; production is not always carried out in accordance with GMP rules; low cost per package. Generics are produced by pharmaceutical companies in Eastern Europe, Asia, Latin America, the CIS, including the Russian Federation. There are tens of thousands of manufacturers of generic drugs worldwide, operating in various economic and regulatory conditions. Therefore, the "cheapness" of a generic often leads to large additional costs for the patient to administer a larger dose of an ineffective generic, treat unwanted side effects and compensate for a more severe clinical condition [1]. Thus, in a randomized study, the effectiveness of several generics of enalapril (Enap, Ednita, Invoril, Envas and Enam) was compared with the original drug Renitec and it was shown that some of them may require certain doses to achieve the effect. almost 3 times higher than the original dose of the drug. In addition, pharmacoeconomic studies of enalapril preparations have shown that a course of treatment, for example, with the "cheap" Enap is significantly more expensive than treatment with the original drug Renitek. When studying the efficacy and safety of generics, Indapamide showed a tendency to increase blood pressure in the first 6-7 hours and 17-19 hours after their use, did not normalize the circadian rhythm of blood pressure and had a pronounced negative trend. effect on electrolytes. Metabolism is not typical for the original indapamide [3]. When comparing the original drug Bisoprolol with one of its generics in patients with arterial hypertension stage 1-2, it was found that the generic significantly reduces systolic and diastolic blood pressure, but this decrease was significantly less (by 3-4 mm Hg) than the decrease in blood pressure under the influence of the original drug. At first glance, such drugs can be interpreted as therapeutically equivalent, but in arterial hypertension, the frequency of

achieving target blood pressure values with the use of the original drug was more than 20% higher than with general use. A randomized, double-blind comparative study of the original drug amlodipine (Norvasc) and one of its many generics, Cardiopin, in patients with mild to moderate arterial hypertension showed that there are no statistically significant differences in body weight in the disease. A hypotensive effect of both drugs was found, but there was a slight tendency to decrease diastolic blood pressure 6 weeks after the start of treatment with Norvasc. This. Cardiopin is the only generic amlodipine that has been fully studied for other generics, without a direct comparison of therapeutic equivalence with the original drug [4,5].

Thus, when choosing a drug, two questions arise:

1) What should I prescribe - the original drug or a generic? 2) If the choice is made in favor of a generic, which manufacturer should be preferred? If you can afford to buy an original drug, it is better to buy the original version. If you have a choice between several generics, it is better to buy a drug from a trusted manufacturer.

In the future, original drugs will take a leading place in the pharmacotherapy of complex cardiovascular diseases, including hypertension. The best option for generics are generics produced in Eastern Europe, since these are mainly modern drugs with a patent protection period of no more than 5 years. Generics produced in Russia and Asia are usually outdated, because ... Their patent protection expired 10-15 years ago

References:

1. Zhukova D.Ya., Kovalskaya G.N. Original and generic drugs in therapeutic practice // Siberian Medical Journal (Irkutsk). - 2011. - No. 7. - B.96-102.
2. Shostak N.A., Rashid M.A., Arinina E.E. In middle-aged patients Efficacy and safety of Bisogamma and Concor for the treatment of arterial hypertension // Farmateka. - 2008. - No. 12 (166). - B.81-89.
3. Kutishchenko N.P., Yakusevich V.V., Deev A.D. The level of therapeutic equivalence of the original indapamide and generic indapamide in patients with arterial hypertension according to rational pharmacotherapy in cardiology. - 2007. - No. 2. - B.26-30.
4. Belolipetsky N.A., Tolpygina S.N., Zverkov Yu.B. Study of clinical and pharmacokinetic equivalence of original and generic amlodipine in patients with mild and moderate arterial hypertension // Rational pharmacotherapy in cardiology. - 2007. - № 5. - B.39-44.
5. Martsevich S.Yu., Kutishchenko N.P., Deev A.D. Study of therapeutic equivalence of two amlodipine preparations (original and generic) in patients

with arterial hypertension. Results of a double-blind randomized crossover study // Russian Journal of Cardiology. - 2004. - № 4. - B.53-57.

6. Tolpygina S.N., Martsevich S.Yu., Shilova E.V. Bisoprolol preparations in a comparative study of the efficacy and tolerability of the original drug in patients with mild and moderate arterial hypertension // Cardiovascular therapy and prevention. - 2007. - № 6. - B.15-21.

7. Nedogoda S.V., Marchenko I.V., Chalyabi T.A. Comparative antihypertensive efficacy of general angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors enalapril-renitek (Enap, Ednit, Invoril, Envas and Enam) and the cost of treating patients with arterial hypertension // Arterial hypertension. - 2000. - № 1. - B.52-54.

